

UTILIZATION OF NATIONAL GUARD CYBER FORCES IN TITLE 32 STATUS FOR NATIONAL CYBER MISSIONS

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ABSTRACT

There has been a debate for more than a decade in the United States about the precise role National Guard and Reserve military forces, and the National Guard in particular, can and should play in cyberspace operations. There are legal, policy, doctrinal, organizational, cultural, and bureaucratic issues that must be overcome or understood to employ National Guard forces for national cyber operations. Leaders in Congress, U.S. Cyber Command, and the National Guard have clearly articulated the need to leverage the cyber expertise in the National Guard in defense of the nation. Papers, articles, and hearings have repeatedly examined the existing landscape and proposed various solutions, including legislation and new organizations, but none has resulted in the type of comprehensive understanding required to clearly assign national cyberspace missions and functions while in Title 32 status beyond training. The National Guard is uniquely positioned as a reserve force with a dual federal and state status, and has over 4,000 cyber personnel with deep expertise in cyberspace operations and cybersecurity. In this dissertation we will examine the many proposals for solutions to date, with limited progress. This dissertation examines the existing law, policy, doctrine, and operational practice governing the use of National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for national cyber missions. Using a multi-method qualitative design that integrates documentary analysis, a practitioner survey, and a focused case study, the study identifies where current authorities enable Title 32 mission support, where implementation barriers persist, and what governance mechanisms are needed for repeatable execution.

Keywords—cyber; cyber operations; cyberspace operations; defensive cyberspace operations; CO; DCO; DoDIN; cybersecurity; military; Army; ARNG; ANG; NG; NGB; National Guard; Title 10; Title 32; RC; reserve component integration; military cyber policy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Executive Summary

This dissertation examines how the United States can more effectively employ National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status to support national cyber missions — particularly defensive missions — at scale and in a repeatable, legally sound manner. The study addresses a persistent problem of practice:

The United States lacks a consistently understood and consistently executed legal–policy–operational pathway to use Title 32 authorities for national cyber mission support beyond training, resulting in underutilized cyber capacity, uneven governance, and inconsistent resourcing and approval processes (see Section 1.3).

Purpose and Approach

The research investigates two questions: (RQ1) what elements of law and policy support or constrain Title 32 cyber mission support; and (RQ2) what precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge such use. The study uses a multi-method qualitative design with embedded descriptive quantitative analysis, integrating:

- **Documentary analysis** of statutory authorities, DoD/NGB policy, joint doctrine, and precedent (coded as enabling, conditional, or constraining).
- A structured **expert survey** fielded June–October 2025 (151 respondents; 60 complete responses), combining Likert/0–10 items with nine open-ended prompts.
- A focused operational **case study** of the Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) as an applied Title 32 mission-support pilot.

Together, these sources are used to assess whether and how Title 32 can support national cyber missions when training remains the paramount purpose and mission support is incidental to training.

Core Findings and Themes

Across all three data sources, the findings support the dissertation's central proposition: National Guard cyber forces can support certain national defensive cyber missions in Title 32 status if a training requirement is met under existing law and policy (see Section 5.2).

1) Existing authorities are more enabling than commonly assumed. The documentary record indicates that existing statutes and policy already support training-aligned operational support under Title 32, with most reviewed sources coded as enabling or conditionally enabling and none strictly prohibitive. A practical pathway centers on 32 U.S.C. §502(a) and (f) (routine training and additional duty) combined with DoD policy and precedent that treat mission outputs as permissible **incident to training** when properly scoped and documented (see Section 4.2).

2) Practitioners view Title 32 as feasible for specific mission types, but not without governance fixes. Survey respondents most strongly identified DoDIN operations and DCO-IDM as feasible under Title 32 with training alignment:

- DCO-IDM—Cyberspace Defense: 86.2%
- DoDIN Operations—Cyberspace Security: 86.2%

Support was more mixed for DCO-RA and OCO actions (Q10). Respondents also strongly agreed that Title 32 activities can be structured to meet training requirements *and* contribute to national mission objectives (55.9% strongly agree; 28.8% agree) (Q11).

At the same time, confidence that Title 32 can support national cyber missions without new legislation was moderate (mean 5.67/10), suggesting the barrier is often implementation clarity rather than statutory absence (Q18).

3) The dominant barriers are implementation ambiguity and institutional friction, not categorical legal prohibitions. Reflexive thematic analysis of open-ended responses produced five major themes:

1. Legal and policy ambiguity
2. Precedent exists but is poorly recognized
3. Operational feasibility and high training value
4. Cultural and institutional resistance
5. Demand for a federated cyber program

The most frequent subthemes were: **lack of implementing guidance** (31.4%), **national–state linkages** (28.1%), and **training–task alignment** (22.9%), followed by **active component bias** and **service parochialism** (see Section 4.4).

4) WIFCP demonstrates a workable Title 32 mission-support model and highlights force-management value. The WIFCP case study documents recurring, training-aligned mission support to a DoD partner in Title 32 status oriented to cybersecurity research and situational awareness. WIFCP also yielded strong mission-partner feedback (e.g., repeated statements that reporting was valuable and used for briefing/analysis) and an observed retention signal: two enlisted cyber Soldiers attributed reenlistment decisions to having meaningful real-world mission work in drilling status, representing an estimated \$800,000 retention impact based on stated replacement costs (see Section 4.5).

Key Recommendations

The dissertation's recommendations are organized into three clusters and explicitly trace to Chapter 4 evidence via a recommendation traceability matrix (see Section 5.4.4).

A) Organizational and Structural Clarify and institutionalize roles and relationships for Title 32 cyber support (see Section 5.4.1):

- Designate clear points of responsibility within U.S. Cyber Command and the National Guard Bureau for Title 32 cyber integration.
- Formalize mission manager roles for federated cyber programs (analogous to federated mission management constructs used elsewhere).
- Encourage state-level cyber integration working groups (TAG, state J-staff, key unit leaders) to align state and federal priorities.

B) Governance and Implementation Treat Title 32 cyber utilization as a cybersecurity risk governance problem and operationalize it with repeatable processes (see Section 5.4.2):

- Develop a formal "Title 32 Cyber Integration Profile" that specifies mission categories appropriate for Title 32 support (e.g., DCO-IDM, DoDIN Ops, cybersecurity situational awareness) and the conditions/expected outcomes.
- Establish standardized request/approval artifacts (templates for training alignment, legal review, and oversight).
- Create standardized metrics and reporting (e.g., number of federated programs, training hours logged on mission, mission impact assessments) to enable oversight and congressional visibility.

C) Strategic Alignment and Policy Development Explicitly align Title 32 cyber integration to national strategy and doctrine (see Section 5.4.3):

- Develop a National Guard Cyber Integration Strategy describing how Title 32 supports national objectives, how it relates to the Cyber Mission Force, and how it contributes to broader multi-domain posture.
- Use FY26 NDAA-directed questions as a roadmap for assessing authorities, leveraging civilian-acquired skills, and identifying billets/infrastructure and barriers.
- Incorporate lessons from pilots like WIFCP into joint/service doctrine/policy so federated Title 32 models become recognized options rather than one-off experiments.

Conclusion

The dissertation concludes that the United States does not primarily face an authority gap for employing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for certain defensive national cyber missions; it faces a governance and execution gap. Documentary evidence, practitioner consensus, and the WIFCP operational proof-of-concept converge on the same implication: a deliberate, structured Title 32 cyber integration approach is both feasible and necessary to scale Guard cyber capacity for national missions while preserving the training-first requirement and sustaining the force through meaningful work and retention benefits (see Chapters 4 and 5).